

A DIGITAL SINGLE SIDEBAND MODULATOR FOR A DIGITAL RADIO FREQUENCY MEMORY

Captain Thomas M. Foltz (AFIT/ENG)
 Captain Gregory W. Cook (WRDC/AAWW-2)
 Lieutenant Colonel David E. Meer, Ph.D. (AFIT/ENG)
 Wright Patterson AFB, Ohio

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to verify that a digital single sideband modulator can be incorporated into a Digital Radio Frequency Memory (DRFM).

The single sideband modulator is designed to use digital multiplying integrated circuits to produce the frequency shift rather than analog mixers. The circuit also employs a digital Hilbert transform filter to shift the phase of the incoming signal by 90 degrees.

The circuit was tested with simulated S-band radar signals ranging from 3.012 to 3.038 GHz. The circuit, running in double sideband mode, proved its ability to shift the frequencies of the radar signals by frequencies in the range of -25 to +25 kHz. All the spurious outputs of the system were found to be more than 28 dB below the carrier.

1 Introduction

Digital Radio Frequency Memories (DRFMs) form a significant building block in modern avionics systems. Typically, a DRFM will sample a radio frequency (RF) signal and then store the signal digitally. At a later time, the stored signal is recreated at RF and then usually modulated to create an offset frequency.

This paper shows that a digital single sideband modulator could be incorporated into a digital RF memory to create a frequency shift in the stored signal. Current DRFM design practices use digital circuitry to sample and delay the received radar signals, but rely on precisely balanced, analog, RF mixers to shift their frequencies. A digital single sideband modulator eliminates the need for the RF mixers because it performs the frequency shift on the digital data. By replacing the analog RF hardware with digital circuitry, the size and weight of an avionics device in an aircraft can be reduced. The spurious spectral outputs of the digital circuitry should also be lower than those of the analog hardware, because the spectrum of the analog hardware is degraded by the presence of strong intermodulation products in the mixer output.

2 Overall System Design

The digital single sideband modulator is capable of altering the frequencies of a signal which has been down converted to fall between 12 and 38 MHz. It can shift the frequencies of this signal in 25 Hz steps up to a maximum of 25.6 kHz. The modulator was designed so that the level of any spurious emission is 30 dB below the level of the desired signal.

The modulator consists of a demultiplexer and multiplexer to process the digitized radar signal in parallel, a Hilbert transformer to shift the phase of the incoming signal by 90 degrees, a frequency synthesizer to generate the Doppler frequency, a multiplier to mix the signal with the Doppler frequency, and a summer to add the signal to its phase shifted version. These subsystems, along with the A/D and D/A converters, are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Digital Single Sideband Modulator

2.1 Demultiplexer/Multiplexer

The demultiplexer is used to slow down the data rate from the 100 Megasamples per second which are input from the A/D converter. The data rate must be slowed down because the circuitry which processes and stores the data is not as fast as the sampler on the A/D converter.

The demultiplexer fans the data out into eight parallel directions so that each of the eight lines contains the data that was present for one of the previous samples.

The multiplexer performs the inverse function of the demultiplexer. It converts the parallel data lines back into a continuous individual bit stream which is input to the D/A converter.

2.2 Hilbert Transformer

The Hilbert transformer converts the phase of the incoming time samples by -90 degrees for positive frequencies and by +90 degrees for negative frequencies. The frequency spectrum of the output of an ideal Hilbert Transformer can be expressed as

$$Y(f) = \hat{X}(f) = \begin{cases} -jX(f) & f \geq 0 \\ +jX(f) & f < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{X}(f)$ represents the Hilbert transform of $X(f)$ [4, 54].

2.3 Frequency Synthesizer

The frequency synthesizer generates a sine and a cosine function whose frequency is the Doppler frequency which will modulate the radar signal. The synthesizer produces digital words which represent sampled values of a sine and cosine. The system can synthesize 1024 frequencies ranging from 0-25.6 kHz in 25 Hz steps.

2.4 Multipliers

The multipliers represent the main difference between this circuit and conventional Digital RF Memories. This circuit uses digital multipliers to perform what otherwise would be accomplished with analog mixers. The data words and cosine words are multiplied with one set of multipliers, and the Hilbert transformed data words and the sine words are multiplied with another set of multipliers.

2.5 Summer

The summer adds the output of the cosine multiplier to the output of the sine multiplier. If the signal is to be shifted up in frequency, the sine multiplier output is subtracted from the cosine multiplier output. The two are added if the signal is to be shifted down in frequency. This is the equivalent of producing the upper or lower sidebands of a signal.

3 Discrete Hilbert Transforms

There are two very subtle differences between the generalized ideal Hilbert transformation expressed in Equation 1, and the ideal discrete Hilbert transform. They result from the difference between the aperiodic frequency spectra of continuous signals and the periodic frequency spectra of discrete time signals, and the differences between the convolution integral for continuous signals and the convolution sum for discrete time signals.

The frequency relationship expressed in Equation 1 is obtained from a system whose impulse response is $h(t) = -1/(\pi t)$. The Hilbert transform relationship for time signals is given by the convolution integral

$$y(t) = \hat{x}(t) = h(t) * x(t) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{x(\gamma)}{\gamma - t} d\gamma \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{x}(t)$ denotes the Hilbert transform of $x(t)$, $*$ represents convolution, and γ is the variable of integration [3, 340].

For discrete time sequences, the Hilbert transform frequency relationship is slightly different, because the spectra of discrete signals are periodic between $-\pi$ and $+\pi$. Oppenheim and Schaffer give the frequency response of an ideal Hilbert transformer as:

$$H(e^{j2\pi F}) = \begin{cases} -j & 0 \leq F \leq 1/2 \\ +j & -1/2 \leq F < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $e^{j2\pi F}$ is used to represent frequencies of discrete time sequences [6, 359]. The impulse response sequence now becomes:

$$h(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{2 \sin^2(\pi n/2)}{\pi n} & |n| > 0 \\ 0 & n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $|n|$ is the absolute value of n , and $n = \{\dots, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ [6, 360]. As shown in Figure 2, the Hilbert transformer has an infinite impulse response and is noncausal.

The second major difference arising for discrete time Hilbert transforms is that $y(n)$, the output sequence, is given by the convolution sum

$$y(n) = \hat{x}(n) = h(n) * x(n) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} h(n-m)x(m) \quad (5)$$

where $h(n)$ is given by Equation 4 [6, 12].

The Hilbert transform of the sequence $x(n)$ cannot be taken from Equation 5 directly because $h(n)$ is the infinite impulse response of a noncausal system. In practice, $h(n)$ is truncated to some odd value N and shifted to the right $(N-1)/2$ samples until the left most value is at the origin. This introduces a delay in the output sequence and an additional linear phase shift in the spectrum of the output. The truncated, shifted impulse response is then usually multiplied by a smoothing window to reduce the effects of nonuniform convergence caused by truncating the infinite series [6, 239].

Figure 2: Hilbert Transform Impulse Response

4 Design of Subsystems

The circuitry in the modulator must be able to process data across the wide bandwidth of 12 to 38 MHz. The A/D card takes 100 million samples of analog data every second, and even fanning the data out eight parallel ways puts a heavy burden on the circuit to keep up. This forces the use of emitter coupled logic (ECL) components because they are among the fastest silicon digital Integrated Circuits (ICs) commercially available.

4.1 A/D-D/A Card

The A/D-D/A card is a preassembled circuit board, built by TRW, housing a TDC1029 6-bit flash A/D converter and a TDC1018 eight-bit D/A converter. The board is designed for ECL logic levels and is capable of being clocked at frequencies up to 100 MHz. This results in 100 million samples of data every second for ideal input signal bandwidths of up to 50 MHz [2, E61].

4.2 Demultiplexer

The demultiplexer is used to create eight parallel lines for each of the six data lines from the A/D converter.

Each of the six data lines is input to a four-bit shift register. The last shift register output line is input to another four-bit shift register as shown in Figure 3. Both shift registers are clocked at the same rate at which the data is sampled, resulting in eight parallel time samples of the data.

After the eighth time sample has been shifted to the bottom most line, all eight of these lines are latched with two more four-bit shift registers used in the latch mode instead of the shift mode. This allows the data to be present on each line for eight clock cycles before being refreshed.

The timing line used to enable the latches which freeze the data for eight time samples is as shown in Figure 4. The counter uses the sample clock as an input, and outputs square waves whose frequencies are a half, a quarter, an eighth, and a sixteenth of the clock frequency.

The NOR gate output line is input to a flip flop clocked with the sample clock so that its inverted output goes low every time the counter counts to seven or fifteen. This line goes low almost immediately after the count of seven or fifteen is reached, because the propagation delay across the high speed ECL flip flop is about 0.7 ns. [1, 6-14]. This is the line used to enable the output latch of the demultiplexer.

Figure 3: Shift Register Demultiplexer

Figure 5: Hilbert Transform Demultiplexer

Figure 4: Timing for Demultiplexer

4.3 Hilbert Transformer

After demultiplexing, the data is sent to an in-phase channel and a quadrature channel, the latter of which computes the Hilbert transform of the data. The data in the quadrature channel is first demultiplexed again to sixteen time samples, so that a longer impulse response may be used by the Hilbert transform filter. The filter structure is derived from the convolution sum of Equation 5, with the coefficients obtained by windowing the impulse response of Equation 4. The filter is implemented using an overlap and save technique, and the data processed using multiplications, additions, and subtractions. The data is then multiplexed to four time samples before being sent to the multipliers.

4.3.1 Hilbert Transform Demultiplexer

The eight time samples entering the Hilbert transformer are demultiplexed to sixteen time samples using latches as shown in Figure 5. The latch in the lower left hand corner is clocked once every eight cycles, and the other two output latches are clocked every sixteen clock cycles, so that sixteen distinct time samples appear on the output.

4.3.2 Convolution Sum Structure

Because there are sixteen time samples available for processing, and since all even values of the impulse response are zero, the convolution sum of Equation 5 reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(n) = & h(-7)x(n+7) + h(-5)x(n+5) + h(-3)x(n+3) \\
 & + h(-1)x(n+1) + h(1)x(n-1) + h(3)x(n-3) \\
 & + h(5)x(n-5) + h(7)x(n-7)
 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $y(n)$ is the output, the $x(n)$'s are the inputs, and the $h(n)$'s are the values of the impulse response. In the impulse response of Equation 4, $h(n) = -h(-n)$, therefore Equation 6 can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(n) = & h(7)[x(n-7) - x(n+7)] + h(5)[x(n-5) - x(n+5)] \\
 & + h(3)[x(n-3) - x(n+3)] \\
 & + h(1)[x(n-1) - x(n+1)]
 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

It is impossible to implement the filter of Equation 7 directly because it is noncausal. To avoid this dependence on future values of the input, a delayed version of $y(n)$ may be computed from:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(n-7) = & h(7)[x(n-14) - x(n)] + h(5)[x(n-12) - x(n-2)] \\
 & + h(3)[x(n-10) - x(n-4)] + h(1)[x(n-8) - x(n-6)]
 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

A graphical representation of this filter structure appears in Figure 6. The expression z^{-2} refers to a delay of two samples. This filter structure agrees with that published by Haykin and Eng [5, 564].

4.3.3 Truncated Impulse Response

The coefficients of the Hilbert transform impulse response must be quantized to six-bits so they can be processed by the circuit in the same manner as the data. If the impulse response of Equation 4 is simply truncated to a length of 15 and then quantized, the filter coefficients will be as given in Table I.

Figure 6: Serial Filter Structure

TABLE I
Truncated Filter Coefficients

n	h(n)
-7	- 3/32
-5	- 4/32
-3	- 7/32
-1	- 20/32
1	+ 20/32
3	+ 7/32
5	+ 4/32
7	+ 3/32

All other values of $h(n)$ are zero.

The frequency response of this filter can be derived from the fact that the impulse response can be viewed as positive and negative going delta functions, the Fourier transform of which is a sum of sine functions. The frequency response is then given by:

$$H(F) = -j \left[\frac{20}{32} \sin F + \frac{7}{32} \sin 3F + \frac{4}{32} \sin 5F + \frac{3}{32} \sin 7F \right] \quad (9)$$

This frequency response is plotted in Figure 7. The plot was generated using a 1024-point Fast Fourier Transform of the impulse response which produces the same result as plotting Equation 9 directly.

Figure 7: Truncated Frequency Response

4.3.4 Windowed Impulse Response

The frequency response in Figure 7 is unacceptable because the large ripples in the passband will produce outputs with a much larger or smaller amplitude relative to the in-phase data. This results in ineffective cancellation of the undesired sideband which will appear in the output spectrum as an image which exceeds the -30 dB design specification for spurious outputs. The smoothness of these ripples can be improved at the expense of a narrower passband. This is accomplished by windowing the impulse response of the filter with a Hamming window of length fifteen.

A Hamming window was chosen because it produces the flattest frequency response over a maximum bandwidth of usable frequencies compared with other common windowing functions. The window length of fifteen arises from matching the length of the impulse response of the Hilbert transform filter to the sixteen data points available for processing, and then neglecting the impulse response value of zero at $n = 8$.

The equation of a Hamming window for a causal sequence is [6, 250]

$$w(n) = 0.54 - 0.46 \cos \left[\frac{2\pi n}{N-1} \right] \quad 0 \leq n \leq N-1 \quad (10)$$

When this window is applied to the impulse response, and the resulting coefficients are quantized to six bits, the impulse response appears as in Table II.

TABLE II
Windowed Filter Coefficients

n	h(n)
-7	0
-5	- 1/32
-3	- 4/32
-1	- 19/32
1	+ 19/32
3	+ 4/32
5	+ 1/32
7	0

All other values of $h(n)$ are zero.

The frequency response of this windowed impulse response is again the sum of sines, and is given by

$$H(F) = -j \left[\frac{19}{32} \sin F + \frac{4}{32} \sin 3F + \frac{1}{32} \sin 5F \right] \quad (11)$$

This frequency response is plotted in Figure 8, again using a 1024-point fast Fourier transform.

Figure 8: Windowed Frequency Response

This windowed frequency response has a sufficiently flat passband to meet the system spurious specification of -30 dB. To meet this specification, the magnitude of the frequency response must fall between 0.98 and 1.02. This condition occurs for 52% of the 50 MHz ideal bandwidth of the system, which translates to a usable bandwidth of 12 to 38 MHz.

4.3.5 Overlap and Save Filter Implementation

The impulse response coefficients were quantized to zero for $h(7)$ and $h(-7)$, so that now only a delay of five samples is required to make the filter causal. Substituting the actual coefficient values into Equation 8, the input output relationship can now be expressed as:

$$y(n-5) = \frac{19}{32}[x(n-6) - x(n-4)] + \frac{4}{32}[x(n-8) - x(n-2)] + \frac{1}{32}[x(n-10) - x(n)] \quad (12)$$

The circuitry is not fast enough to compute the output values serially, as depicted in Figure 6. Instead each value must be computed in parallel, requiring sixteen separate circuits to implement Equation 12 sixteen times, once for each output value $y(n)$.

The Hilbert transform filter uses latches at the input to save an additional ten samples, so that a data point exists for each point in the impulse response. This method of convolution, which prevents the impulse response from wrapping around the data in a circular convolution, is called the overlap and save method [6, 113-115].

4.3.6 Multiplications

Each of the sixteen parallel stages of the Hilbert transform filter must implement three multiplications as expressed by Equation 12.

Figure 9: Multiplications by 1/32 and 1/8

Multiplication by 1/32 and by 4/32 is very easy because both coefficients can be expressed as powers of two. These multiplications can be implemented by shifting the positions of the bits as shown in Figure 9 where "Dn" refers to the data, and "Pn" refers to the product.

Multiplication by the coefficient 19/32 can be viewed as multiplication by the sum of the powers of two which add to 19/32. These are 1/32, 1/16, and 1/2, each of which can be achieved by shifting the positions of the bits in the word to be multiplied. The resulting multiplication network appears in Figure 10, where each AND-XOR gate combination is a half adder, and the plus signs inside the circles represent full adders with carry inputs.

Figure 10: Multiplication by 19/32

4.3.7 Additions and Subtractions

The additions and subtractions of Equation 12 are carried out using MC10180 full adder/subtractors made by Motorola [1, 3-142]. To prevent an overflow in two's-complement addition, the least significant bit is dropped from the input, and the sign bit is repeated in the upper two registers [7, 12-13]. This method produces a six-bit result.

The overall implementation of Equation 12 is shown in Figure 11. The multiplications for the coefficients of 1/32 and 1/8 are performed before the first addition stage, because they quite easy to implement. For the multiplication by 19/32, the data words are first added, then the multiplication is performed. The filter uses sixteen parallel stages like those shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Hilbert Transform Filter

4.3.8 Hilbert Transformer Multiplexer

The sixteen time samples present at the output are multiplexed down to four time samples which persist for one fourth as long. This multiplexing is achieved using four to one multiplexing chips. The outputs of the multiplexers are latched.

4.4 In-Phase Multiplexer and Delay

The eight time samples of data, which are processed in parallel with the quadrature Hilbert transformed data, are multiplexed down to four time samples using two-to-one multiplexing chips. The four time samples are then delayed with latches to compensate for the time it takes to calculate the Hilbert transform values and to make up for the shift of five sample periods needed to make the Hilbert transform filter causal.

4.5 Frequency Synthesizer

The six-bit sine and cosine words of a full cycle are stored in a 64kx16 bit Random Access Memory (RAM) manufactured by Integrated Device Technologies. The data is loaded into the RAM from a Motorola 68020 computer which also controls the frequency shift of the modulating circuit.

After the data is loaded into the RAM, the address lines of the RAM are controlled by adders and latches, as shown in Figure 12. The ten-bit frequency word sent from the 68020 is added to the 16-bit output of the latches, which is sent to the RAM as the address. The latches are clocked at 1.6 MHz, so that the output data from the RAM will appear as samples of frequencies that are multiples of 25 Hz.

All the circuitry for the frequency synthesizer is made of TTL devices, so the sine and cosine outputs are converted to ECL logic levels before being multiplied with the data.

Figure 12: Frequency Synthesizer Address

4.6 Multipliers

The DRFM requires four Motorola Large Scale Integration (LSI) MC10901 eight-bit multiplier chips to multiply the in-phase data with the cosine samples and four identical multipliers to multiply the Hilbert transformed quadrature data with the sine samples. The LSI chips are capable of multiplying two eight-bit words in about 17 ns [1, 6-14].

The sine and cosine samples are latched to synchronize them with the in-phase and quadrature data and prevent them from changing during the middle of a multiply. The sine and cosine samples change a maximum of 1.6% as fast as the other data changes, so the same sine and cosine samples are used for all four multiplies even though the in-phase and quadrature data will represent four different samples.

4.7 Summer

The outputs of the multipliers are added or subtracted depending on whether a positive or negative Doppler shift is required. The adder/subtractor chips are the same as used for the Hilbert transformer. As before, the least significant bit is dropped, and the sign bit is sent to the upper two registers to avoid an overflow.

The subtract line on the adders is tied to a line from the 68020 which has been converted to ECL logic levels, and is high for a positive frequency shift and low for a negative frequency shift. Figure 13 shows how this line is also sent to the lowest register carry input. The data inputs are represented by "An" and "Bn," the subtract line is represented by SUBTR, and the sum is represented by "Sn."

Figure 13: Summer

4.8 Multiplexer

The circuit uses four-to-one multiplexing chips to reduce the four time samples from the output of the adders back to single time samples which are present for only as long as the period of the sample clock. The chips used to perform this multiplexing are high speed versions of the same chips used by the Hilbert transformer multiplexer. The multiplexer outputs are latched before being sent to the D/A card.

4.9 Packaging

The circuit is built on eleven circuit cards and is housed in three rack mounted boxes. The interconnections between the cards, boxes, and test equipment are made from RF semi rigid cable, twisted pair lines, and ribbon cable.

5 System Testing

This section describes how the digital single sideband modulating circuit was tested using S-band sinusoidal signals. Only the in-phase portion of the circuit was constructed to date. The test procedures and results used to measure the double sideband outputs are described below, including test procedures using S-band radar signals to be used after the Hilbert transformer is built.

5.1 Test Procedures

The circuit was tested with sinusoidal input signals at frequencies of 2.966, 2.972, 2.978, 2.984, 3.016, 3.022, 3.028, and 3.034 GHz. When these test signals are mixed with the local oscillator frequency of 3.000 GHz, they all fall within the IF passband of 12 to 38 MHz as constrained by the Hilbert transform filter.

The circuit was tested at each of the eight test frequencies, and the Motorola 68020 was programmed to control the frequency synthesizer so that it produces shifts of 0, 7.5, 15, and 22.5 kHz. The shifts were applied to each of the eight test frequencies resulting in 32 separate measurements.

The S-band test signals were generated with a Hewlett Packard (HP) 8672A frequency synthesizer, while the local oscillator signal was generated with a different HP 8672A. The relative level of any spurious signals in the output of the circuit was measured with an HP 8566B spectrum analyzer. A spectrum analyzer plot of the HP 8671B test signal at 2.984 GHz appears in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Sinusoidal Input Spectrum

5.2 Test Results

The spectral performance of the digital modulating circuit for sinusoidal inputs was compared to the baseline DRFM. A sample of this result is shown in Figure 15. The center frequency for this test signal was 2.990 GHz, and the frequency shift was -15 kHz. The vertical scale is 10 dB/div., and the horizontal scale is 15 kHz/div.

The spurious output at the original (unshifted) center frequency is 26 dB below the shifted output. Other spurious outputs appear at 28 dB and 30 dB below the shifted signal.

As a comparison, the output spectrum of the digital modulating circuit for an input of 2.984 GHz and a frequency shift of -15 kHz appears in Figure 16. The circuit produces two output sinusoids for a single sinusoidal input, because there is no quadrature channel to cancel one of them out. The scales in Figure 16 are the same as the scales in Figure 15.

The strongest spurious output shown in Figure 16 occurs at the center of the two shifted signals and is 28 dB below their power level. The other two spurious outputs are 44 dB below the desired signal level. The central spurious output is slightly lower than the baseline DRFM central spurious output, but the other spurious outputs are significantly lower than the baseline intermodulation products.

The level of the spurious outputs for a given center frequency did not change as the frequency shift was changed. The spurious levels were, however, different for different center frequencies. The spurious output at the center frequency was always the strongest, averaging -30 dB across the band with the strongest at -28 dB.

6 Conclusions

This paper has shown that digital multiplying circuitry could be used to replace RF analog mixers in digital RF memories. It presented the design for a fully digital single sideband modulator, and the test results of the circuit showing that spurious output levels are more than 28 dB below the desired output level.

Through the development of a working prototype, it was shown that similar circuits could easily be added to future digital RF memory designs, greatly reducing the amount of RF hardware required by the system. As digital technology becomes faster, smaller, lighter, and more power efficient, digital single sideband modulators could greatly reduce the payload requirements of airborne systems, while providing them with improved performance.

Figure 15: Sinusoidal Output from Analog Mixing

Figure 16: Sinusoidal Output from Digital Frequency Shift

References

- [1] *Motorola MECL Device Data*. Motorola Inc., 1983.
- [2] *TRW VLSI Data Book*. TRW, La Jolla, CA, 1985. Electronic Components Group.
- [3] V. Cizek. Discrete hilbert transform. *IEEE Transactions on Audio and Electroacoustics*, (18):340-343, December 1970.
- [4] J. Dugundji. Envelopes and pre-envelopes of real waveforms. *IRE Transactions on Information Theory*, (4):53-57, March 1958.
- [5] S. S. Haydin and C. Eng. Different forms of the hilbert transform as applied to digital filters and sequences. *Proceedings of the IEE*, (121):561-567, July 1974.
- [6] A. V. Oppenheim and R. W. Schaffer. *Digital Signal Processing*. Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1975.
- [7] S. Waser and M. J. Flynn. *Introduction to Arithmetic for Digital System Designers*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1982.